

Introduction on the use of the Best4Soil databases

Best4Soil provides information on the host status and damage sensitivity of crops for a large number of nematode species and soilborne pathogens.

The approach is based on the concept of Wageningen UR | Field crops – www.aaltjesschema.nl

Based on this information you can determine the optimal order to grow the different crops.

The trick is to grow a poor host plant preceding a crop that is damage-sensitive to this pest or pathogen. In this way the contamination levels in the year of cultivation of the damage-sensitive crop are low and no damage occurs

The other way round, of course it is not a problem if the infection levels are high at the moment a crop is grown that is not affected by it.

The tool is currently available in all 22 official languages. The tool contains 70 crops, 32 nematode species and 138 soilborne pathogen species. Each nematode - crop combination will get a background page (WIKI) with additional information, photos and do's and don'ts. Also each pathogen will be provided with such a WIKI page.

The working method for the nematode scheme and the pathogen scheme is the same. Click on the DATABASE (PATHOGENS) > or DATABASE (NEMATODES) > button on the bottom of this page and the tool of your choice appears:

1. Choose your language – by choosing a flag, above the Best4Soil logo
2. Choose your Country – this is mandatory.
3. Choose the type of soil – this is mandatory

1

Country: -

Soil Type: -

Description: Description name

CREATE SCHEME

Crops: Select a country first

Crop selection	0
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Nematodes: (de)select all minimize all

Cyst nematodes	09
Root-knot nematodes	07
Root lesion nematodes	04

4. Choose the crops you are growing now or would like to grow. You can choose the same crop several times by clicking on the plus sign.
5. Now you can open the Crop selection above the selected crops. You can change the crop order with the arrows. not pick more than 30 soil pathogens at a time. This could adversely affect the readability of the document. In that case, create a second scheme.
6. Choose the nematodes or soil pathogens that are present in the field. Do not pick more than 30 soil pathogens at a time. This could adversely affect the readability of the document. In that case, create a second scheme.

The screenshot displays the 'BEST4 SOIL' web application interface for creating a 'Nematode scheme'. At the top, there is a header with the logo and navigation links for 'Home' and 'Nematode scheme'. Below the header, there is a search bar and a form with the following fields:

- Country: United Kingdom
- Soil Type: clay soil
- Description: Description name

A green 'CREATE SCHEME' button is located to the right of the description field. Below the form, there are two main panels:

- Crops**: This panel has a sub-section 'Crop selection' with a count of 1. It includes a 'delete selection' link and a list of selected crops: 'Black fallow'. Below this is a 'Field crops' section with a count of 1/20 and a list of crops: Barley, Beet (sugar, fodder), Black fallow (checked), Clover, Faba bean, Hemp, Linseed, Lucerne (= alfalfa), and Lupins.
- Nematodes**: This panel has a sub-section 'Cyst nematodes' with a count of 0/9. Below it is a 'Root-knot nematodes' section with a count of 0/7 and a list of nematode species: Meloidogyne naasi, Meloidogyne chitwoodi, Meloidogyne incognita, Meloidogyne fallax, Meloidogyne hapla, Meloidogyne arenaria, and Meloidogyne javanica.

Three blue arrows with numbers 4, 5, and 6 point to the 'Black fallow' crop, the 'Crop selection' section, and a nematode species respectively.

7. Press the CREATE SCHEME button

8. Open the pdf to view the result.

Nematode scheme 2020

Date : Thursday, October 22, 2020
 Country : United Kingdom
 Description : Database instruction 26 October 2020
 Soil Type : sandy soil

Click on a cell for background information about the crop / nematode combination

	Cyst nematodes										Root-knot nematodes										Root lesion nematodes					Stem nematodes			Free-living root nematodes	
	<i>Gabouleria rostochiensis</i> / Potato cyst nematode	<i>Heterodera avenae</i> Cereal cyst nematode	<i>Heterodera betulae</i> Yellow beet cyst nematode	<i>Heterodera schachtii</i> Beet cyst nematode	<i>Meloidogyne arenaria</i> Peanut root-knot nematode	<i>Meloidogyne chitwoodii</i> Columba root-knot nematode	<i>Meloidogyne fallax</i> Tobacco root-knot nematode	<i>Meloidogyne hapla</i> Northern root-knot nematode	<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i> Cotton root-knot nematode	<i>Meloidogyne javanica</i> Sugarcane root-knot nematode	<i>Meloidogyne naasi</i> (Barley) root-knot nematode	<i>Pratylenchus brachyurus</i>	<i>Pratylenchus ornatus</i> Cereal root lesion nematode	<i>Pratylenchus neglectus</i> Sugarbeet lesion nematode	<i>Pratylenchus pectinarius</i> Northern root lesion nematode	<i>Pityrrhynchus destructor</i> Potato rot nematode	<i>Stem nematode</i>	<i>Trichodorus pratensis</i> Slabby-root nematode	<i>Trichodorus similis</i> Slabby-root nematode											
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	1	2										
Potato	***	-	-	-	?	***	***	***	?	?	-	?	?	?	***	***	***	***	***	***										
Beet (sugar, fodder)	-	-	***	***	?	***	***	***	***	***	?	?	?	?	***	***	***	***	***	***										
Potato	***	-	-	-	?	***	***	***	?	?	-	?	?	?	***	***	***	***	***	***										
Barley	-	***	-	-	?	***	***	***	?	?	***	?	?	?	***	***	***	***	***	***										
Japanese/Black oat	-	?	?	?	?	***	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?										
Marigold	-	-	-	-	?	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***										

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Legend damage

-	unknown
-	none
-	little (0-15%)
-	medium (16-35%)
-	serious (36-100%)

Legend propagation

-	active decline of population
?	host plant suitability unknown
-	non host
•	poor host
••	moderate host
•••	good host
R	variously dependent
S	serotype dependent
I	some information

Legend soil type

1	sandy soil
2	reclaimed peat soil
3	sandy clay loam
4	clay soil
5	silty soil (loess)

9. Troubleshooting

If you press the CREATE SCHEME button and nothing happens:

- Make sure you choose a country and a soil type, these are mandatory
- Check for an ad blocker or pop-up blocker and turn it of (usually found under the gear icon)

- Don't use Internet Explorer but choose another browser like Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox or Microsoft Edge.

For more help, questions or feedback:
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[An instruction video on how-to use the tool is available.](#)
 So come back to this site on a regular basis to follow the progress.